

THE COMPARATIVE SYNTAX OF ÈGBÁ DIALECT AND STANDARD YORÙBÁ LANGUAGE

By

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Abstract

It is my intention in this paper to present the similarities and the differences of the standard Yorùbá language and the Egbá dialect through lexical processes, phrasal categories and syntactic processes. The work will follow the generative grammar approach as Chomsky's (1981) Government and Binding theory, and will substantially utilize existing grammars and examples to give up comparable structures in Egbá dialect for the possible long term exercise in historical linguistics. Today, words in Yorùbá metalanguage are rich and adequate because dialects fill possible gaps. This work will partially show the source of the terms coined by the linguistics. In addition, historical Yorùbá linguistics will benefit from this study when other dialects would have been surveyed and documented. The monolingual method of approach, the Ibadan four hundred word lists was used in collecting my data and some references were made to some books and articles available on the languages.

Introduction

The aim of this work is to give some information about the comparative syntax of Egbá dialect and standard Yorùbá. Egbá dialect and Yorùbá are mutually intelligible, and the former is considered a dialect of the latter. Though we do not expect to find any wide difference in this work, we think little drops here and there from Egbá dialect will enrich the grammar of Yorùbá for whatever purpose. Part of the anticipated difference will be mostly along lexical items with some assuming different usages in the language forms.

We discovered that in the nature of the lexicon every word has idiosyncratic properties and are therefore has to be learnt individually.

However, we hope we shall be able to move close to some generalization. While our data should feed further works by scholars

Historical Background of the Yorùbá

The generations of Oduduwa are referred to as "Yorùbá" and the language they speak is called "Yorùbá language". The original home of the Yorùbá is still obscure. Even renowned author like Johnson seems emotional. Numerous are the stories attached to their origin. One of the stories traced their origin to Egypt while another says the generation descended from Mecca (Saudi Arabia). Considering that most of these stories are tales, it is difficult to dispose one for another but one thing that is certain, is the fact that all the generation (origin) could be traced back to Ile-ife for it is the point where dispersion started.

At first, Oduwa children do not have a general name for which they were addressed though individual tribe has a name for themselves; for instance, Ekiti know them as Ekiti, Egba as Egba likewise the Oyo as Oyo. History has it that it was not the children of Oduwa that gave them the name "Yorùbá" but the foreigners addressed them as such. The first to suggest this name was Clapper ton and Bowditch. "Olukumi and Aku" were the first name given to this generation. The children of Yorùbá whom slave trade took to Sierra-Leone were the first to be called the name "Yorùbá".

It is not only in Nigeria that Yorùbá language is been spoken. Among countries where the language is spoken are: Togo, Trinidad & Tobago, Jamaica, Brazil, Sierra-Leone, Cuba, Liberia and Republic of Benin.

Few among the names given to various settlements with their distinctive dialects are: Oyo, Ekiti, Egba, Ife, Igbomina, Ofa, Ijesa, Ijebu, Ilaje and so on while those who are related to the Yorùbá race in some parts of Nigeria are: Igálà, Itsekiri, Idoma, Igbira, Gbari, Nupe and Edo.

The Yorùbá as a Standard Language

The form of the language dealt with here is 'standard Yorùbá' that is spoken on the radio and used in school text books in Nigeria. Although it was originally based on the dialects of the Oyo area of Nigeria, extreme Oyo regionalism has been removed. Very little work has been published on the varied and numerous Yorùbá dialects; articles and books which are available concentrate on the standard Yorùbá which has a standard and recognized orthography.

However, definite generalized of standard Yorùbá can not be made until more is known of the various dialects, in the mean time, all that a researcher can do is to concentrate upon the speech of one or two particular informants while using others to try to determine what part of their informants speech can most accurately be called "standard".

Historical Background of the Egbás

The Yorùbá sub-ethnic group known as the 'Egbá' sometimes called Egbá-lùgbò were formerly inhabiting a very thick forest far away to river Ogun in their part of the world before they finally moved down to establish a town in 1830, which they named Abeokuta as a result of their settlement under a big hill when they first came. It was this hill that is called Olumo rock and the inhabitant are the part referred to as the 'Egbás' today or Egbá children of Lisabi. Egbá dialect among the native speakers respectively is widely spoken among the people as their mother tongue with little variations. They include Egbá Alake or Egbá Agbehin; Egbá Oke-ona; Egbá olowu and Egbá Gbagùrà.

Nearly every township in the provinces has its own king. But all these kings must make obeisance to the king of the capital towns, and the king of the capital towns were to recognize the Alake as their head. The early region of the Egbá people could not be correctly called fetishism or paganism, for they were aware of and did acknowledge the existence of the Almighty God, whom they call Olorun. The traditional Egbá people were farmers, hunters and traders, they passed their time in peace with the surrounding nations but occasionally with one another. The language of the Egbá people is the Yorùbá language but with certain peculiarities. Even among the Egbá sub-ethnic groups, different subdialects exist. The tone of the language is in itself very musical, fine and intelligent. Proverbs in the Yorùbá language originally belong to the Egbás (Johnson, 1921).

Keeness in trade is bestowed in them. They are shrewd, calculating and hard bargainers. They are also artful, cunning and watchful of strangers whom they serve and deal with. Owing to their early contact with the missionaries, certain traditions have been assimilated. One of such is the mode of dressing. The linguistics influence from the early missionaries' language also positively affected Egbá dialect and tradition. Till today, it is noticed that Egbá people still bear's names like Brown, Coker, and Vaughan etc which they adopted from the whites. The early contacts with the whites also made the Egbá to witness the introduction of Christianity before any other town in the western Nigeria.

SYNTAX AND THE BASIC WORD ORDER OF EGBÁ AND STANDARD YORÙBÁ

This section focused on the definition of comparative syntax and the basic word order of Egbá and standard Yorùbá. According to Stockwell (1977) is to study various aspects of how sentences are formed and how they are understood (i.e. interpreted semantically in a particular language and languages generally.

Syntax is the aspect of grammar which study the arrangement of words to form sentence. Thus:

PHONEME - MORPHEME-WORD-PHRASE-SENTENCE

We lay emphasize on the constituents of Yorùbá phrasal categories since Egbá is a dialect of the standard Yorùbá, the syntactic features of sentences in the two dialects are not very different. The only major difference lies in the lexical items. There is also little or no difference in the phrasal categories of the two dialects. Ample example are given to justify this positions.

The Basic Word Order of Egbá and Standard Yorùbá

The basic word order of the Egbá dialect and Yorùbá language above agree with what the grammar of the language allows. The subject-verb-object (S.V.O) form will be taken as their basic word order which indicates how subject verb and object co-occur in sentences. For instance,

Egbá dialect	Standard Yorùbá	Englis' language
mo wi e	mo sô fún ô/mo wi fun e	I told you
mò ñ re sùkùrù	mò n lô sí sùkùrù	I'm going to school

Word Classes of Egbá and Standard Yorùbá

The notion of part of speech is still a useful one. Though the terms word class is usually preferred these days. It is convenient to talk about classes of words that have some characteristic or order in common. Word classes are generally divided into two broad groups, namely open classes and closed classes. The open classes or lexical level of words are: nouns, verbs, adjective and adverb. The closed classes of words are; pronouns, numerals, determiners, prepositions and conjunctions. For the closed classes, the membership is fixed, it is generally not possible to add new members. But for the open classes the opposite is the case, new members are being constantly added as new words are coined in the science, technology, or by advertisers and sub-cultures.

The Lexical Level

Verb

Verbs, generally refer to action, events and processes. They are doing words which tell us what a noun or pronoun does. Almost every verb in Egbá behave like its counterpart in the standard Yorùbá. It is only few verbs in Egbá that are not attested in the standard Yorùbá language. An example of that is the word "bi" "bear" with a variance of "be" "bear". The former is used for human being while the latter is used for animals as in:

1. Sadé bí omo
2. Ewùrè bé omo

Examples of verb in Egbá dialect and standard Yorùbá are underline below.

Egbá dialect	Standard Yorùbá	English language
Ayo máa <u>yun</u>	Ayo maa <u>lo</u>	Ayo will <u>go</u>

From the examples above many words abound in Egbá that are no longer attested, other than in fixed collocations or stories.

Verbs is equally divided into auxiliary and lexical verbs. Auxiliary verbs are a closed sub-class and have a mainly grammatical function. Examples of the modal verbs are:

Egbá dialect	Standard Yorùbá	English language
De lè	Lè	May

Among the lexical verbs, a distinction is traditionally made between transitive and intransitive verbs. Transitive verbs are those that require a complement, be it Noun phrase or sentence, while intransitive verbs are those that do not take an object/complement, the latter may take a non-obligatory. Meanwhile, in both Egbá and standard Yorùbá, transitive verbs may take any complement, noun phrase or sentence.

Egbá dialect	Standard Yorùbá	English language
bébi	Bèèrè	Ask

Examples of intransitive verbs.

Egbá dialect	Standard Yorùbá	English language
Ródò	Dúró	wait

Noun

Noun generally refer to things in the broadest sense. If we have a noun for something, it implies that we view it as a thing, that is, a process known as rectification. The class of noun is traditionally divided into proper and common nouns. The lexical items that belong to this class behave in the same way in the two languages being compared and their forms is also the same. The majority of these words start with vowels.

Proper nouns refer to unique things, such as people, places or institutions. Examples are:

Egbá dialect	Standard Yorùbá	English language
Tifini	Sítifini	Stephen
Kênèún	Kìniún	Lion
Ewen	Eyin	Egg

While common nouns do not refer to unique things; for instance "plant" does not refer to a unique object, but rather to a class of objects or to a specific instance of that class.

Common nouns are sub-divided into concrete nouns and abstract nouns. Concrete nouns refers to perceivable objects in the world. Example of concrete noun.

Egbá dialect	Standard Yorùbá	English language
Ìkèèmù	Ikéèmù	Cup

While abstract nouns refers to ideas, feelings and things of that kind.

Example of Abstract Noun

Egbá dialect	Standard Yorùbá	English language
Ìdòyì	Wáhálà	Problem

Other types of noun are countable and uncountable. Countable nouns refer to object that may be counted, while uncountable noun are objects that cannot be counted.

Adjective

Adjectives typically give further information about the meaning of nouns or pronouns. There is no difference in the behaviour of the adjective in the standard Yorùbá and that of Egbá dialect. They behave in the same way. The number of adjectives in the language is quite large. The majority, if not all, are derived from verbs and nouns. In formal grammar of Yorùbá, according to Bamgbose (1966) and Yusuf (1995), adjectives are said to be verbs in most cases. Some adjectives are also nouns, if they are not noun, why consonant initial? This is because examples like [díê, gbogbo] could then have been formed by reduplication like 'fifun' 'white' 'púpõ' 'many', diedie.

Preposition

The preposition shows the relationship of a noun or pronoun to some other words in the sentence. Bamigbose (1990) identified only two prepositions; these are: ni 'at' and pèlú 'with'. Awobuluyi (1978) identified seven prepositions; these are: 'with', pèlú 'for', fún, 'from', láti, sí, pèlú 'with' is not attested in Egbá Àárè (one part of Egbá dialect). It is replaced by toun, i.e ti - oun. For instance,

Egbá dialect	Standard Yorùbá	English language
Adé toun Olú wá	Adé pèlú Olú wá	Ade came with Olu
Tòun lèsí wá?	Pèlú ta ló wá?	With whom did he come?

Adverbs

Adverbs represent a very diverse set of words. These are basically two kinds: those which refer to circumstantial information about the action, event or process such as time, place or manner of it and those which serve to intensify other adverbs and adjectives. Examples of adverbs referring to circumstantial information about action, event or process are:

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Egbá dialect	Standard Yorùbá	English language
lèèsenyíí	nísínýíí	Now

While the examples of adverbs that serve to intensify other adverbs and adjectives are:

Egbá dialect	Standard Yorùbá	English language
burú jái	burú jái	extremely rigid/bad

Pronoun

The pronoun is used instead of a noun to avoid repetition of nouns. Pronouns performs the same function as nouns in a sentence. There are sub-classes of pronouns, namely personal pronouns, reflexive pronouns and the possessive pronouns. Personal pronouns refer to the person speaking, the person spoken to and the person spoken about.

Examples of Reflective pronoun

Egbá dialect	Standard Yorùbá	English language
Èmi tìkálárami	èmi fún/tika larami	Myself
Ìwo tìkálárare	ìwõ fún/tika lararaare	Yourself

Conjunctions

Conjunctions as the name implies have a joining function, usually that of joining one clause to another to show a kind of relationship between them. Conjunctions are of two kinds, they are the co-ordinating conjunction which join words or groups that are of the same order or rank.

The second type of conjunction is the sub-ordinating conjunction which subordinates one item to another in some way. However, the subordinate may be one of time, reason or some other kinds.

Disconjunction

Disconjunction is the act of disjoining or condition of being disjoined. Disjunction words are those used for separation, disconnection or disunion of sentences. Examples are:

Egbá dialect	Standard Yorùbá	English language
Àdàbí	Àyàfí	except, but for, apart from
Àmõ/Sùgbon	Sùgbon/Amo	But

Clauses

What is a clause in Egbá dialect and standard Yorùbá?

A clause is a stretch of utterance that has only one finite verb in its structure at the primary degree of delicacy. It is also used to refer to a grammatically coherent linguistic text that has a verb. This verb may be of one linguistic form as in the example below:

Egbá dialect	Standard Yorùbá	English language
Ó fò ife nées nígba yo ñ fò ó	ó fò ife nàa nígba tí ó ñ fò ó	She broke the cup while washing

Generally speaking, clauses may be divided into two main groups, namely, main clause that is referred to as independent clause and subordinate clause known as dependent clause.

Main clause

A main clause is one that expresses a complete thought and can stand by itself as a sentence. For instance;

Egbá dialect	Standard Yorùbá	English language
Mo rí kénéún	Mo rí kìnìún	I saw a lion

However, every sentence will have at least one main clause which gives the main idea of the sentence while some sentences may have more than one main clause which are joined with the help of a conjunction. For example:

Egbá dialect	Standard Yorùbá	English language
Ajá nee lé olóńginní nées, báàré olóńginní né? sí sùré gun igi	Ajá nàa lé olóńgińdí nàa bēē ní Olońgíńńí nàa sí sàré gun igi	The dog chased the cat, and the cat ran up the tree

Subordinate clause:

A subordinate clause is often referred to as a dependent clause. It does not contain a complete thought and cannot stand alone. A subordinate clause is usually

introduced by a linking word of some kind that signals to us that this clause is dependent on the main clause in the sentence. For examples:

Egbá dialect	Standard Yorùbá	English language
Ó gbö péé bàbá àgba òun tí kú	Ó gbö pé bàbá àgba òun tí kú	He heard that his grandfather has Died'

The main clause in the example above is "Ó gbö" (he heard) while the subordinate clause is "tí kú" (has died), and the word "pé" (that) is the linking word that indicates to us that this is a subordinate clause.

Conclusion

This paper was designed to find out some basic background information on aspects of the differences or similarities that can be found in Egbá dialect and standard Yorùbá.

With our observation, one finds that Egbá dialect shares some common features with standard Yorùbá. However, major differences noticed in the area of phonology particularly tone and lexicon are highlighted.

It is my belief that this work will help for further research into other dialect especially with serious implication on the lexicon, which of course has bearing on the semantics. For example certain words are available in Egbá dialect but cannot be traced in standard Yorùbá. In some cases, where such words are common, they may assume a new meaning in Egbá dialect. However, with previous research by lecturers, students and researchers, the aspects of linguistics that is; comparative syntax of Egbá dialect and standard Yoruba language has a solid foundation on which good and encouraging study can be done.

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APPENDIX I

	Ègbá Dialect	Standard Yorùbá	English Language
1	Ìyẹtu	erùpẹ/yèèpẹ	Sand
2	Ẹpọn	Ẹjẹ	Blood
3	Eréékì	Oríkì	family name
4	olùkù	Ọrẹ kòríkòsùn	Best friend
5	Ìmàrò	Alákòwé onígbaǵbọ	church secretary
6	Itùn	Adúgbò	Area
7	àlé ẹyẹ	íté ẹyẹ	Nest
8	iwín	ìgbé/ìmín	Feaces
9	ẹrun	Ẹnu	Mouth
10	òtẹ	ìgbà	time/season
11	Bá a wà	béẹ̀ ní	Yes
12	ìgbìì	ìgbà tí	When
13	Í í kí?	ó ní kí nì?	he said what?
14	Adí	Aṣe	So
15	dẹhìn wá	padà wá	come back
16	ń fùwà	hùwà	Behaving
17	ṣe màrò	ẹsìn onígbaǵbọ	Christian worship
18	lèsí yèn?	tanì yèn?	who is that
19	ródò dèmí	dúró dèmí	wait for me
20	yó' tí	mu ọtí yó	got drunk
21	Adíkò yún	Aṣé kò lọ	so he didn't go
22	B'ógànjọ kò ǵán	Bí ilẹ̀ kò sù	if it's not late
23	jùgbòṅ ọrò	sọkò ọrò	To say abusive words
24	Bí só yún?	nìbò lẹ̀ lọ	where did he go to?
25	Olfyèn	ẹni náá/olúwarẹ	the person